

DECHEMA

Gesellschaft für Chemische Technik
und Biotechnologie e.V.

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Ihre Nachricht von

Your letter of

Ihr Zeichen

Your Reference

Unser Zeichen

Our Ref

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Datum Frankfurt am Main, 15 May 2025

Date

CONFIRMATION OF PARTICIPATION

It is herewith confirmed that

Ana B. Pereiro

took part in the conference

**PPEPPD - International Conference on Properties and Phase Equilibria for Product and Process Design
11 - 15 May 2025, Bad Gögging**

Kind regards

Nina Weingärtner